

Dissemination and exploitation plan – updated M18

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ABSTRACT

The dissemination and exploitation plan summarizes the consortium's strategy and the concrete actions that should be made in order to disseminate and exploit the results generated by the project. Dissemination activities are going to be performed during the whole project lifetime and are not going to be an after-thought. This deliverable is the 18-month revision of the plan submitted in month 6. The dissemination and exploitation plan will be updated again at month 36.

This document, version 04, has been revised to account for the comments received in the project review after the first reporting period.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
2 INTRODUCTION.....	5
2.1 About the project and its objectives	5
2.2 Objective of the exploitation and dissemination activities.....	6
3 OUTCOME OF WIDER UPTAKE.....	6
3.1 Results.....	6
3.2 Innovations.....	7
4 DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS.....	8
4.1 Exploitation and dissemination strategic principles	8
4.2 Target groups	8
4.2.1 Water/wastewater utilities and city decision-makers	9
4.2.2 Local stakeholders	9
4.2.3 Scientific community	9
4.2.4 European and National policymakers	9
4.2.5 Citizens	10
4.3 Dissemination and exploitation content	10
4.3.1 Dissemination content per WP	10
4.3.2 Dissemination content per solution and outcomes	10
4.4 Tools and channels	10
4.4.1 Logo and visual identity	10
4.4.2 Website	11
4.4.3 Social media	12
4.4.4 Information materials	12
4.4.5 Publications	12
4.4.6 Audio-visual marketing materials	14
4.4.7 Conferences and events.....	14
4.4.8 Multipliers & synergies.....	14
4.4.9 Media relations	15
4.4.10 EC channels and tools	15
4.4.11 Policy brief and recommendations	16
5 OPEN ACCESS AND DATA MANAGEMENT.....	16

6 INVOLVEMENT OF POTENTIAL END-USERS AND STAKEHOLDERS IN WIDER UPTAKE.....	17
7 BARRIERS TO IMPLEMENTATION OF RESULTS FROM WIDER UPTAKE	17
8 IMPLEMENTATION OF RESULTS BEYOND PROJECT COMPLETION ...	18
9 EDUCATION OF YOUNG PROFESSIONALS AND RESEARCHERS	18
10 MONITORING AND EVALUATION OF ACTIVITIES.....	19

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Preliminary identification of Scientific Journals	13
Table 2: Events and conferences.....	14
Table 3: Tools made available by the European Commission to H2020 projects	16
Table 4: Summary of WIDER UPTAKE dissemination activities	20
Table 5: Summary of WIDER UPTAKE exploitation activities.....	23

1 Executive summary

The dissemination and exploitation plan describes measures for the dissemination and exploitation of WIDER UPTAKE's results, and KPIs for measuring the activity.

The WIDER UPTAKE project aims to have an impact in the water and wastewater sector. The expected impact will rely on new industrial symbioses based on water-smart solutions that will link water and wastewater treatment, resource extraction, energy supply and product development for the agriculture, building & manufacturing materials industries, and energy supply. It is expected that the results of WIDER UPTAKE project will provide measures to overcome the existing barriers (social, economic, political) hampering the application of circular economy concepts to the water and wastewater sector. Five demonstration cases will demonstrate explicitly how it is possible to achieve the recovery of resources from water and wastewater in symbiotic circular economy relationships between utilities and industries.

The outputs of WIDER UPTAKE project will consist of a roadmap with recommendations and of a set of measures to be applied for the achievement of optimized water-smart systems. Moreover, another output of the project will consist in the realization of policy briefs enhancing the barriers overcome. The outputs of the project will be made available through a series of standard and advanced dissemination methods. In particular, seminars and training activities will be held during the project and a final conference will summarize the main outcomes/achievements of the project, the acquired knowledge, the policy implications, and recommendations; scientific papers will be published in open access or peer review journals, with the aim to disseminate and make available the ongoing results of the project. Scheduled events and workshops will be organized in order to deliver the project outcomes fostering them to provide their feedback. Printed and on-line material will be produced in order to inform public and stakeholders, whilst the construction of WIDER UPTAKE social media and website will keep all the interested actors updated for all implemented and planned future activities and outcomes of the project. Deliverables produced as documents will be archived in the WIDER UPTAKE website with open access for interested persons and organizations.

In accordance with D7.4 – Communication plan, as well as the work performed under WP4, Task 4.2, the target groups to disseminate and exploit the project outcomes to have been identified as: water/wastewater utilities and city decision-makers, business organisations, city networks and association, scientific community, European and national policy makers, and citizens. Young professionals and students are also an important target for the dissemination activities in the project as they represent the future of the water sector.

Particular attention will be also paid on the exploitation, that will specifically be designed in order to multiply the impact of the proposed solutions and prepare the transition towards industrial and commercial uptake in order to fully achieve the expected impact.

2 Introduction

This document is developed as part of the WIDER UPTAKE project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme, under the Grant Agreement number 869283.

The purpose of the present dissemination and exploitation plan is to define and establish an effective framework which will guide the dissemination and exploitation activities throughout the project. This plan will contribute to the successful implementation of the project and reinforce the project's potential impact on policy and management. A preliminary version was provided at M6, and revised versions are planned on month 18 (this version) and month 36 of the project.

All exploitation and dissemination activities will be carried out in accordance with the Grant Agreement and be aligned with the communication activities described in D7.4 – Communication plan.

2.1 About the project and its objectives

WIDER UPTAKE main goal is to facilitate industrial symbiosis as a mean to increase resource efficiency, limit emissions and develop sustainable business based on water-smart solutions. The project's hypothesis is that the barriers for wider uptake of water-smart solutions are not only technological but also of organizational, regulatory, social, and economic character.

WIDER UPTAKE will identify and demonstrate common measures to overcome barriers related to:

1. 'Monitoring and control of health and quality risks'
2. 'Circular-economy and efficiency potential'
3. 'Governance and business models for industrial symbiosis'
4. 'Measuring water smartness and progress towards SDG'.

The project includes demonstrations at five different locations/countries/settings of:

- Wastewater reuse for agriculture and urban greening
- Phosphorus recycling, biogas, and biochar utilisation
- Production of bio composites for manufacturing materials with resources recovered from the whole water cycle.
-

The partnership in WIDER UPTAKE includes 11 water utilities and industries and 7 research institutes or universities, distributed across 5 countries (Norway, Netherlands, Czech Republic, Italy, and Ghana).

The WIDER UPTAKE project aims to have an impact in the water and wastewater sector. The expected impact will rely on new industrial symbioses based on water-smart solutions that will link water and wastewater treatment, resource extraction, energy supply and product development for the agriculture, building & manufacturing materials industries, and energy supply. It is expected that the results of WIDER UPTAKE will provide measures to overcome the existing barriers (social, economic, political) hampering the application of circular economy concepts to the water and wastewater sector.

2.2 Objective of the exploitation and dissemination activities

According to the grant agreement, the exploitation and dissemination plan objective is to support the local partners in case-specific activities, to support companies in further development of symbiotic CE solutions, and to ensure knowledge transfer and uptake of WIDER UPTAKE main outcomes among citizens, utilities, policymakers, and the scientific community. More specifically, the objectives of exploitation activities are to i) Promote novel industrial symbiosis among the involved industrial stakeholders; ii) Promote the future creation of new companies/industrial activity focused on the CE and smart cities concept. Dissemination aims at maximizing the impact of research results in the public domain.

There are some specific communication objectives:

- SO6.1: to develop and implement a roadmap for wider uptake of water-smart solutions,
- SO6.2: to develop measures for exploitation of project results after the project period has ended,
- SO6.3: to promote a new market based on the water-smart system vision
- SO6.4: to disseminate the knowledge acquired

This deliverable represents the established plan to achieve the objectives SO6.2 and SO6.4.

The dissemination and exploitation plan of WIDER UPTAKE summarizes the consortium's strategy and the concrete actions that should be made in order to disseminate, exploit, and protect the results generated by the project. Dissemination activities are going to be performed during the entire project lifetime and are not going to be an after-thought. This deliverable is the 18-month revision of the plan submitted in month 6. The dissemination and exploitation plan will be updated again at month 36.

3 Outcome of WIDER UPTAKE

3.1 Results

The WIDER UPTAKE project will have two types of results: i. direct results; ii. indirect results.

Direct results will be:

- The improved understanding in terms of processes operation acquired by means laboratory and on-site (within the real plants) experimental tests.
- Mathematical models able to describe each part of the plants under study and to support their optimal operation in view of reducing the energy and resources employment according to a CE concept.
- Publications which summarize the results of the project published in the most relevant international journals that will be made available to the scientific community.
- Creation of a new market between Ghana and Sicily where products or sub-products of the project will be shared.
- A roadmap towards a water-smart society and related manual that includes all the mathematical models, set-up and calibrated, and all the knowledge acquired (social, economic, technical, and experimental) during the project.

- A framework for monitoring and controlling health and quality risks that can account for the multi-actor contributions to the risks in symbiotic relations between water utilities and industries in a circular economy context.
- A framework for Circularity and Efficiency Assessment and Optimisation of Symbiotic Solutions
- A tool for Governance assessment for circular economy based on water resources.
- A framework for holistic assessment of water smartness and progress towards SDGs
- A set of policy briefs enhancing the barriers to overcome.

Indirect results will be:

- Materials (nutrients) recovery, sludge, and water reuse from wastewater treatment plants.
- Reduced energy usage from wastewater treatment plants.
- Reduction of bio solids production in wastewater treatment plants.
- Improvement of the stakeholders' awareness on the economic, environmental, and social convenience in commercializing the products of the project (such as materials).

The roadmap creation represents the key and novel direct result of the project since it summarizes all the direct and indirect results in a pathway towards the achievement of a water smartness and a shift to circular economy.

3.2 Innovations

The innovations in WIDER UPTAKE can be grouped in two groups. The first is existing innovations that already have been, and are developed, by the industry and partly utility partners in the case studies, e.g., new bio composite material, 3D printed raingarden boxes, novel biofilm process for EBPR, novel adsorbents for nutrient recovery, biochar fuel products to replace charcoal or wood as fuel. These innovations are at different levels of maturity and the further development of the innovations themselves and the business plans, IPR-management and other measures required for exploitation will be performed by the industry partners of the Consortium, e.g., Hias How20, HØST, NPSP, Storm Aqua, etc. in collaboration with the utilities.

These exploitation measures will be supported by WIDER UPTAKE activities but are not solely dependent on the project as such because the companies and utilities would anyhow be developing these measures as part of their already defined business model. The support activities in WIDER UPTAKE in Task 6.2.1 will be organised as part of the Communities of Practice (CoP). Business model development will be addressed specifically through WP4, task T4.2.2, which will explore innovative CE business models and test their applicability in the different demonstration cases. The aim is to facilitate further development of symbiotic solutions and to co-develop strategies for widespread implementation of these, thereby furthering market uptake of the technical innovations.

The other group of innovations in WIDER UPTAKE are the tools related to the methodologies for overcoming the barriers for wider uptake of water-smart solutions that are developed in the project. Exploitation of these tools in the project will be done as part of the activities in the respective WPs for the tools and in the case studies. Wider exploitation of the tools by external users and after the project end should be addressed in the next revision of exploitation and dissemination plan. These tools will have open access and the measures to secure exploitation of these will therefore be focused on informing the various

potential users about the tools and providing means of access to the tools that will be effective also after the end of the project. The exploitation and dissemination plan of WIDER UPTAKE reflects the characteristics of the two groups of innovations and is focused on supporting the sharing of non-proprietary information – in the consortium and externally – and disseminating the results to a wide group of recipients.

4 Dissemination and exploitation of results

4.1 Exploitation and dissemination strategic principles

The following set of strategic cross-cutting principles will underpin the dissemination, communication, and exploitation efforts:

1. **Focus on the solutions rather than on “the project”.** The end goal of WIDER UPTAKE is to demonstrate innovative solutions for wastewater reuse and resource recovery where market utilisation of the recovered resource(s) (water, nutrients, materials, energy) is achieved through a symbiosis between the utility and industry. The exploitation and dissemination activities will reflect the commercial and business nature of these solutions in circular water management. This will be most tangible in the revised design of the project website which will be tuned more towards solutions than project.
2. **Stories** will be key in making the benefits of the solutions tangible to their target audience. The communication will focus on highlighting the positive aspects (services, benefits; added value to companies/citizens) instead of the more ‘negative’ ones (threats from climate change, for example) through storylines that resonate with daily lives and working processes.
3. **Establish a recognizable and attractive brand identity.** A recognisable visual identity and brand has been developed for WIDER UPTAKE, ensuring its suitability for both the project and commercial phases.
4. **Focus communication towards specific, targeted audiences.** Instead of large-scale communication, the focus will be set on reaching out to specific actors. The utilities and technology providers will be interviewed to test the unique selling propositions and narratives. While tailoring the dissemination plan for each story, WP6 will still ensure that the results are brought together in a coherent way to enable their exportation to areas outside their case studies.
5. **Leverage multipliers to maximise impacts.** Networks, organisations, relevant individuals, or media have the potential to greatly boost the project communication efforts. While the initial target groups have been identified, the list of target audiences will be further developed throughout the project.

4.2 Target groups

Carefully defining the target audiences is the key to getting the messages across. There are five target groups for WIDER UPTAKE (in alignment with the Communication plan, D7.4):

- Water/wastewater utilities and city decision-makers,
- Stakeholders (e.g., business organisations, city networks and association, etc.),
- Scientific community,
- European and national policy makers,
- Citizens.

This section describes these target groups in more detail, outlining communication objectives, narratives, and key messages for each. The initial set of key messages has been defined during the update of this plan in M18 of the project and will be further refined in the next update in M36. In M36 these will be complemented by specific value propositions, targeted at exploitation and market uptake of the solutions, and defined in collaboration with WP4, which will form the basis of the final communications campaign during the last phase of the project. WP6 will further align with and benefit from the mapping of stakeholders performed by Task 4.2.

4.2.1 Water/wastewater utilities and city decision-makers

Water/wastewater utilities and city decision-makers are the direct beneficiaries and potential users of most of the WIDER UPTAKE solutions. The **specific communication objective** in relation to this group is market uptake, replication of the technologies as well as capacity building and raising awareness about the solutions demonstrated in WIDER UPTAKE.

4.2.2 Local stakeholders

The stakeholders' category includes regional/local authorities, private companies, end users, business organisations, city networks and association, etc. Task 4.2 has already identified a list of local stakeholders per demo site which will be addressed.

The **specific communication objective** in relation to this group is to raise awareness about WIDER UPTAKE and engage for further dissemination and co-development of the solutions. The CoP (Task 7.3) will be the crucial channels to reach this target audience.

4.2.3 Scientific community

The third audience is the scientific community who will use the information and results to exchange on urban water management challenges, building on the WIDER UPTAKE findings and results. This scientific community refers to the research community working in the field of treatment/processing technologies, circular economy in the water sector and water and energy management.

The **specific communication objective** in relation to this group is exploitation of results in further scientific discussions and research.

4.2.4 European and National policymakers

The fourth target audience are the European and National policymakers. The WIDER UPTAKE results will lead to the formulation of policy recommendations that will be disseminated towards the policy audience who will make decisions on the enabling policy frameworks. More precisely, they refer to:

- National Ministries/Departments of Environment/Science & Technology
- European Commission DG DIGIT, ENV, REGIO, AGRI, GROW
- MEP Water Group, Water JPI
- MEPs active in the project's issue areas
- European level associations such as Water Europe, EIP Water, EIP Agri.

The **specific communication objective** in relation to this group is the implementation of the WIDER UPTAKE policy recommendations for short- to medium-term policy developments in the EU and case study countries.

4.2.5 Citizens

The last category are citizens who will directly benefit from the environmental and societal benefits brought by the WIDER UPTAKE solutions.

The **specific communication objectives** in relation to this group are to make the public aware about urban water issues, to foster the public use and social acceptance of circularities enabled by WIDER UPTAKE.

4.3 Dissemination and exploitation content

The content will evolve as the project progresses. At the beginning, the content will primarily focus on the expected benefits of each solution. The focus will increasingly shift to the concrete outcomes of each solution and their market uptake in all over the EU.

As each result, presented in section 3.1, is different, specific messages linked to the values, interests and motivations of the target groups will be developed. We aim to develop solution-specific value propositions, stories, linked with the business model canvas (of WP4).

4.3.1 Dissemination content per WP

Our dissemination actions will reflect the strategic milestones of the project and our aim is to make sure that all relevant outcomes resulting from the different WPs are communicated to their targets.

The information will be communicated to all the target groups. However, as said earlier, the messages will be tailored to fit the characteristics and needs of each audience and the best channels will be chosen in order to reach them in the most relevant way.

4.3.2 Dissemination content per solution and outcomes

The solutions are at the heart of the project. Therefore, developing specific messages, value propositions and stories linked to the motivations of those who use these solutions is important also in view of further exploitation.

While the messages to be communicated will evolve with the progress of the project, a first set of messages/storylines will be developed. WP6, Task 6.2.1 will coordinate the process with each solution developer from 2022, in a process aligned with the business model development in WP4 and in parallel with further development of the website content.

4.4 Tools and channels

4.4.1 Logo and visual identity

In order to maintain a cohesive image and make the project and its outputs readily identifiable, a project logo and a corporate design has been created by the partner SINTEF, (Figure 1). This logo is displayed in all project materials, such as website, social media profiles, leaflets, conference presentations, publications, videos, etc.

Figure 1 WIDER UPTAKE logo

Concomitantly, templates for Word documents, PowerPoint presentations and publications (such as reports) were made available for partners.

According to the Grant Agreement and general EU research funding rules, any dissemination of results must acknowledge EU Horizon 2020 funding, by displaying the EU emblem, with appropriate prominence, and including the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869283”.

Also, any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. It is recommended to display the following text in any report or another kind of publication:

“The publication reflects only the authors’ views, and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.”

For presentations the following text should be used in the same manner:

“This presentation reflects only the authors’ views, and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.”

4.4.2 Website

The public project website is available since Month 3 at: <https://www.wider-uptake.eu> and has been revised after the project review in February 2022 to focus on results, deliverables, and activities in the demo cases, while still providing information about the project, objectives, and the consortium. The webpage is continuously updated with results and project news (in blog format). The website allows to promote, among other things, project materials, press releases, publications, project results for download, as well as links to social media channels and it will also host the Virtual Learning and Sharing Centre for Water-Smart Solutions (Marketplace). Links to partner websites and relevant organizations are featured. Visitors can subscribe for the newsletter.

Local websites in local languages have also been created, with specific information about the local demonstration cases and country specific information, see the following link of local websites:

Italian: <https://wideruptake.unipa.it/home>

Prague: <https://wider-uptake.webnode.cz/>

4.4.3 Social media

A Facebook and a LinkedIn account were established:

- <https://www.facebook.com/groups/489234269105783/about/>
- <https://www.linkedin.com/company/wider-uptake>

The social media accounts have been regularly updated with news items from the project. At the time of writing, the project profile on Twitter has 431 followers and on LinkedIn 46 followers.

Social media #wideruptake (Facebook, LinkedIn, and twitter) has been used by UNIPA to disseminate project results:

<https://m.facebook.com/WiderUptakeUnipa/>

<https://twitter.com/WiderUptake>

4.4.4 Information materials

WP7, Task 7.4, will make available information material such as brochures and factsheets made available in the project website in printable version, so to be downloaded and handout by Partners during events on need.

4.4.5 Publications

The WIDER UPTAKE team will prepare and submit at least 15 articles to scientific journals open access (gold option); it is foreseen that the publications will cover specific results at demo case level, as well as the horizontal topics of WIDER UPTAKE, such as the smartness-assessment framework and the risk assessment approach.

The most suitable journals for each content will be selected based on the following criteria:

- Open access options
- Scientific impact
- Disciplinary and methodological fit

A tentative list of scientific journals to which WIDER UPTAKE articles may be submitted is in Table, which will be updated throughout the project. It is foreseen that the updated version of this report, as M36, will also include national journals. Due to the timings of peer-review and scientific publication, we expect to have 10 articles submitted and under revision by the end of the project, with publication dates in the following two or three years. The WIDER UPTAKE team will also seek to publish other kinds of scientific publications, such as book chapters and edited issues of journals or monographies whenever possible.

Table 1: Preliminary identification of Scientific Journals

EU/ international	Bioresource Technology Environment Technology Environmental Engineering and Management Journal Environmental Management Environmental Science: Processes & Impacts European Journal of Sustainable Development International Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health International Journal of Water Resources Development IWA Publishing AQUA IWA Publishing Blue-Green Systems IWA Publishing H2 Open Journal IWA Publishing Water & Health IWA Publishing Water Policy IWA Publishing Water Practice and Technology IWA Publishing Water Quality Research Journal IWA Publishing Water Reuse Journal IWA Publishing Water Science & Technology IWA Publishing Water Supply IWA Publishing Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development Journal of Environmental Management Journal of Environmental Psychology Land Use and Planning Local Environment Membranes (MDPI) Procedia Engineering Research Involvement and Engagement Resources, Conservation & Recycling Science Communication Science of the Total Environment Separation & Purification Technology Strategic Management Journal Sustainability (MDPI) Urban Water Journal Water (MDPI) Water Research Water Resources Management Water Reuse & Desalination
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Furthermore, WIDER UPTAKE will make use of the new open access publication outlet of the European Commission: [Open Research Europe](#). This is an open access publishing platform for the publication of research stemming from Horizon 2020 funding across all subject areas. This will allow us to comply with the open access terms of the funding and seems to be a promising venue to share results and insights swiftly and to facilitate open, constructive research discussion.

Regarding the research data generated by the research activities, the partners will deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) the data. This includes associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible, and other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the ‘data management plan’. They will also provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the partners and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves). The management of these data will be made in

accordance with the Project’s DMP and in compliance with the EU Intellectual Property Rights Regulations.

This will be done strictly in conformity with the obligations of maintaining anonymity, confidentiality, security and protecting personal data. Data archiving will make use of the services provided by OpenAire (www.openaire.eu) and ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org/>) where the WIDER UPTAKE has established a dedicated repository.

4.4.6 Audio-visual marketing materials

In the first 18 months the project has produced five videos of which four in the form of interviews to the partners (<https://youtu.be/H2pF9W2UnmE>, <https://youtu.be/7GFR1Riyiwg>; <https://youtu.be/OOSdVw41IKk>; <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0heVu-gkx7I>) and one as an animated video presenting the WIDER UPTAKE general concept (WIDER-UPTAKE.UNIPA). During next reporting period, the project will produce videos showcasing the success stories and the main results of the project.

4.4.7 Conferences and events

Due to the covid pandemic conferences and events during the first 18 months have been local/national events with participation of WIDER UPTAKE limited to the partners of the five demonstration cases. At the revision of the dissemination and exploitation plan, the covid situation seems to be changing and planning for participation in physical events is again feasible. Table 2 provides a non-exhaustive list of events where participation from WIDER UPTAKE is planned. To date the IWA WWCE 2022 and WE events have been selected. New upcoming conferences will be screened at each update of the Communication Strategy and added to the list in the table.

Table 2: Events and conferences

Title of the event	City	Country	Start date	End date
IWA World Water Congress and Exhibition 2022	Copenhagen	Denmark	2022/09/11	2022/09/15
WATER EUROPE EVENTS	Brussels	Belgium	Annual events	

The consortium has an event page on the WIDER UPTAKE website ([News & Events \(sintef.no\)](http://News & Events (sintef.no))) to promote water and CE-related events, and it will soon add a feature to indicate where the project is being presented.

Seminars and training workshops dedicated to the project partners were also planned. In the first 18 months of the project WIDER UPTAKE, these have been organised as part of the CoP activities in WP7, Task 7.3 and are included in the report on CoP-activities (D7.6). This activity will continue in the next reporting period.

4.4.8 Multipliers & synergies

Connections with other similar projects will be actively sought. The WIDER UPTAKE team has assessed which H2020 projects, especially in the same and related calls, have commonalities in market domain and technical implementation with the scope of mutual

scientific exchange, common dissemination, support in organizing events of mutual interest and coordination of input to standardization activities.

The current list of ongoing projects with which collaborations is being explored is given below:

- B-WaterSmart - Water-smart economies and societies
- ULTIMATE: industry water-utility symbiosis for a smarter water society
- WATER MINING Next generation water-smart management systems: large scale demonstrations for a circular economy and society
- REWAISE RESILIENT WATER INNOVATION FOR SMART ECONOMY

Those four projects are funded under the same call as WIDER UPTAKE, and from the very beginning the five coordinators have actively collaborated by starting a process of systematically mapping commonalities in terms of topics, case studies, technologies, methodological frameworks, target regions, and stakeholders. This has led to the creation of the network CIRSEAU. A regular exchange (every three months) between coordinators takes place. Between the CIRSEAU projects, there are now different cross-cutting topic groups on which ideas are exchanged (e.g., on "Communication", "Assessment Methods", "Stakeholder Engagement", "Young Water Professionals"). There are exchanges and joint event activities between the Young Water Professional Groups of the individual projects. Furthermore, the CIRSEAU projects have submitted a joint workshop proposal to the IWA WWCE 2022.

Additionally, the opportunities of building from the findings of the following past H2020 projects will be investigated:

- FIWARE for the Next Generation Internet Services for the WATER sector: in relation to interoperability and data models.
- NextGen Towards a next generation of water systems and services for the circular economy: in relation to CE results and the marketplace for exploitation purposes.
- STOP-IT Strategic, Tactical, Operational Protection of water Infrastructure against cyber-physical Threats: in relation to water security and risk management.

4.4.9 Media relations

We will map city and national media contact points (through the Partners and CIRSEAU working group on dissemination and communication) and undertake soft sounding¹ and other communication techniques to maximise the service positioning.

4.4.10 EC channels and tools

Any relevant opportunity to communicate and disseminate the project activities and results via the EC and Horizon 2020 communication channels, including social media, will be considered to help raise the profile of the project and reach out to a wider audience. The WIDER UPTAKE Coordinator will maintain regular communication with the Project Officer and inform about interesting news, results, and events.

¹By “soft-sounding” we refer to contacts with journalists (which take place prior to e.g. the publication of a specific press release) to gauge their interest in the project or an issue.

In addition, we will consider using some of the free tools made available by the European Commission to H2020 projects, such as presented in

Table 3: Tools made available by the European Commission to H2020 projects

Publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Horizon Magazine • Project stories • research*eu results magazine • research*eu focus • Newsletters
Audio visual	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Futuris Magazine - EuroNews
Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events on the CORDIS website
Online news	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Headlines on Commission's Research & Innovation website • CORDIS Wire

4.4.11 Policy brief and recommendations

In months 24 (D7.7) and 44 (D7.9), the project partner SINTEF will issue briefs for policy developments based on the findings in the cases studies. WP6 will support the dissemination of these recommendations by publication of the file on the WIDER UPTAKE website and sharing in social media. All the partners will also support the dissemination of the recommendations by distributing them during EU or national policy events.

5 Open access and data management

As mentioned in section 4.8, a very important aspect is to guarantee the open access of the achieved results and data management. Indeed, all projects receiving Horizon 2020 funding are required to make sure that any peer-reviewed journal article they publish is openly accessible, free of charge (article 29.2. Model Grant Agreement). Specific measures to provide open access, including for instance the Gold open access, will be carried out by using a portion of the budget to each partner in WP6 for open access publication. Moreover, the Green open access (or self-archiving) will be implemented, by imposing that the final published paper or the final revised manuscript will be archived by the researcher in an online repository, before, alongside or after its publication.

WIDER UPTAKE will make use of the service provided by OpenAire and of the Zenodo repository² as the main tools to make our research data findable in accordance with the H2020 Open Access Mandate. A WIDER UPTAKE community has been established in the Zenodo repository, and the project will upload all our public datasets and deliverables as well as scientific publications to this community once they are approved by the EU Commission. Additional information regarding FAIR data management and Open Access for results from WIDER UPTAKE is included in D7.2 Data management plan_draft.

The Data Management Plan includes instruction regarding data sharing and accessibility in Open Access. Moreover, a description of the procedures to be adopted for the preservation of data in the short and long term is provided there.

² <http://help.zenodo.org/> (DOI versioning)

6 Involvement of potential end-users and stakeholders in WIDER UPTAKE

The WIDER UPTAKE project cases studies are characterized by symbiotic relations between utilities and industries. There will in addition be other stakeholders (e.g., public agencies, user groups) that together with the project partners will be crucial for the exploitation of the innovations. The close connection between project partners and stakeholders involved in the cases will be of huge importance for the developing the project roadmap that will aid in achieving improvement of the market uptake. With a strict commitment from the early stage of the project, end-users and stakeholders will help the project partners to guide the work towards applications.

The engagement of stakeholders and end-users (industries, professionals, public administration, academic, etc.) will be beneficial not only for achieving success in the project, but to stakeholders themselves. Interconnections will be created by sharing industrial, marketing, and commercial protocols according to the novel vision of “circular economy” market in the wastewater sector towards wider uptake of water-smart solutions.

The active use of the CoP that have been established in the project, at local level, project level and trans-project, are instrumental to promote this involvement.

7 Barriers to implementation of results from WIDER UPTAKE

Several barriers exist during the creation of innovative circular economy solutions involving water utilities and private businesses from industry sectors. These barriers represent the obstacles that the project aims to overcome. Among these barriers the most relevant are:

- Regulatory and institutional barriers which prevent the wide application of developed innovative solutions.
- Skills shortages within the wastewater treatment plants according to the circular economy concept.
- Traditional value chains that are less keen to innovate.
- Mismatch between market needs and the solution.

During the WIDER UPTAKE project, the awareness of the existing barriers will be spread among all the involved partners and stakeholders. Further, economics, business, marketing, and public administrations will be involved during the project as supporters for selecting the best actions to take in view of overcoming these barriers. For example, the public administrations will support the breaking down of the regulatory and institutional barriers in view of opening to the adoption of innovative solutions for using the recovered materials (nutrients, sludge) and water in agriculture. In this regard, several actions will be carried out: organization of discussing tables among the stakeholders (universities, project partners, municipalities, administrations, technical politics), workshops. The involvement of economics and business managers will allow the information of the market stakeholders on the advantages of commercializing the project products and sub-products.

The present covid pandemic represents a short-term barrier to implement the results of this project, as most of the events until month 18 have been conducted digitally. Nevertheless, the efforts to spread the results will continue, either in a digital form or as physical events as soon as it is feasible.

Developing countries may present peculiar challenges in dissemination and exploitation of results that may be addressed by innovative approaches. WIDER UPTAKE will use the case in Ghana to employ a novel dissemination approach specifically suited for the context in a developing country. Four critical actors will be prioritised to cover the entire chain of stakeholders required and in a set of dedicated events (seminars, workshops, demonstrations, field visits, participation in fairs and exhibitions, etc.).

8 Implementation of results beyond project completion

The results obtained from WIDER UPTAKE will be implemented beyond the project completion by sharing the roadmap and all the knowledge acquired during the project. This will be achieved by establishing a Virtual Learning and Sharing Centre for Water-Smart Solutions (VLSC). The VLSC will be part of the project website and built as a community portal for networking and sharing data, tools, case studies and publications.

Specifically, an accurate database will be available online in the VLSC containing all the best solutions (according to the circular economy concept) obtained during the roadmap application in the case studies considered during the project. These data will guide the potential future users on the actions to implement in their systems towards water smartness and sustainable conditions.

Further, all the documents produced during the project (papers, roadmap user manual, mathematical models, and user manual) will be available online in the VLSC and shared with the scientific community and market potential stakeholders.

However, the VLSC will be more than the collection of documents and data from the project activities. It will be designed to provide virtual showcases of the symbiotic solutions in the project and provide users with the opportunity to develop their own symbiotic solution in a virtual space. In the process the users will be able to follow the roadmap in an interactive manner and access the relevant tools and guidance along the way. The VLSC will be a key measure for sharing of information and exploitation of results WIDER UPTAKE.

An opportunity, that recently emerged under the collaboration in CIRSEAU, and that will be investigated by WP6, is to directly link or even better embed the VLSC with the Knowledge Portal (Marketplace) for solutions, information, training for water-smart CE solutions, developed across multiple projects in the past H2020 and now being used by ULTIMATE and B-WaterSmart. WP6 will investigate this opportunity which has the benefit to ensure sustainability beyond the project since the knowledge portal will be permanently operated by Water Europe after the project.

9 Education of young professionals and researchers

An important opportunity, in particular for the academic partners in WIDER UPTAKE, is to utilise all the dimensions in the project to promote the education of the next generation of stakeholders in the water sector and to prepare them for the transition into water smart solutions: young researchers and professionals and students at all levels: master, PhD's and Post Doc.

The high interdisciplinarity in the project and the possibility to compare similar technical solutions in different geographical, economic, and social contexts has an enormous educational value, to be taken advantage of.

WIDER UPTAKE has created an internal network among their PhD students and young practitioners called "Young Water Professionals". There are in total 17 young professionals per today in WIDER UPTAKE. In addition to creating a stronger link across the academic institutions in the project, the young professionals have expressed the value of having such a multidisciplinary network among them. Further, the academic partners in WIDER UPTAKE can make use of this internal network to invite master students to link their master projects to the topics and cases in WIDER UPTAKE. In addition, the international Water Association, in particular their dedicated network *IWA Young Water Professionals*, will be used as a channel for dissemination. WIDER UPTAKE will also look at synergies among the Young Professionals networks in the other SC5-04 projects by way of leading the YWP working group in CIRSEAU.

Finally, creating awareness around WIDER UPTAKE and a related identity among young professionals will contribute to create the necessary critical mass for the transition into industrial symbiosis for water smart solutions.

10 Monitoring and evaluation of activities

Continuous evaluation is necessary to analyse the effectiveness of the actions taken, in order to optimise future actions. We will regularly monitor the effectiveness of the exploitation and dissemination activities and consider the use of different and/or additional channels if considered necessary. Both quantitative and qualitative indicators will be considered.

To facilitate monitoring and assessment, all partners will be requested to:

- Prepare and update their individual action plans
- Conduct their dissemination and communication activities according to the global and individual action plans
- Keep the WP6 leader UNIPA updated about their dissemination activities as well as report on their activities during the update of the action plans (which actions were implemented, what supplementary activities were performed) and in the periodic reports to the EC.
- All partners should keep evidence of their implemented activities.

The following quantitative and qualitative KPIs have been defined to measure the effectiveness of the dissemination activities undertaken.

Table 4: Summary of WIDER UPTAKE dissemination activities

Dissemination activity	Methodology	KPI	Target (End of the project)	Results Month 18	Results Month 36
<i>Project website</i>	<i>Google analytics</i>	Number of total visits	>30,000	Not reported	
<i>Social media /</i>	<i>Twitter analytics LinkedIn Campaign Monitor</i>	Interactions with Twitter and LinkedIn accounts.	600 followers 100 retweets 50 comments	431 followers on Twitter, 46 followers on LinkedIn	
<i>Videos (Vimeo)</i>	<i>Vimeo/YouTube analytics</i>	No of animated videos published	1	1	
		No of demo case videos published	5	4	
<i>Media presence</i>	<i>Dissemination reporting (Excel)</i>	No of articles/press releases published	30	20	
		No of articles/papers published	15	2	
<i>Conferences & Events</i>	<i>Dissemination reporting (Excel)</i>	No of external events attended by WIDER UPTAKE partners	30	6	
		No of events organized at demo sites	At least one communication event at each demonstration site during the lifetime of the project	3	
<i>Synergies & multiplier contacts</i>	<i>List of related initiatives/projects /multipliers identified and proof of contact</i>	No of synergies/contacts	10	1 (composed of 4 projects)	

wider uptake

D6.2 – Dissemination and exploitation plan_updated M18

<i>Newletter</i>	No of newsletter published	No of newsletter published /month	1 every 6 months	2	
<i>Workshops Including training activities and summer schools</i>	<i>Dissemination reporting (Excel)</i>	Number of workshops and participants	3 workshops/year	6	
<i>Policy briefs</i>	<i>Policy brief produced</i>	Number of policy briefs	2	None yet, planned for later in the project	

In addition to the above activities, WIDER UPTAKE is engaged in the publication of a book by Elsevier publishing. The tentative title is *Current Developments in Biotechnology and Bioengineering - Smart Solutions for Wastewater: Road-mapping the Transition to Circular Economy*. The intention of this publication is to provide students and professionals with a knowledge base around the topics covered in WIDER UPTAKE. Access to this knowledge base can represent an inspiration for practitioners, students, and young professionals to actively contribute to the transition to a circular economy with water smart solutions.

Table 5: Summary of WIDER UPTAKE exploitation activities

Measure or activity	Methodology	KPI for the measure or activity	Target (End of the project)	Results Month 18	Results Month 36
Supporting companies in the further development of their business plans	<p>WIDER UPTAKE will set up and execute a plan for industrial network development, closely linked with the demonstration cases.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A triple-layered business model canvas for dialogue-based assessment and identification of specific symbiosis models for the demonstration cases will be applied. ○ Important aspects in an industrial symbiosis will be addressed in workshops for each demonstration case, coordinated with WP1. <p>For the case studies in the project this will be part of WP4 and WP1.</p>	No. of new/improved business plans for the participating industries	5	None yet, planned for later in the project	
Improve symbiotic solutions	<p>WIDER UPTAKE will use the tools developed in the project to analyse the symbiotic solutions according to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Health and safety management tool ○ Optimisation of resource efficiency and value chains ○ Governance assessment ○ Holistic assessment of sustainability <p>For the case studies in the project this will be part of WP2-5 and WP1.</p>	Progress towards SDGs as measured by WP5 tool	N/A, based on the WP5 results	None yet, planned for later in the project	

<p>Supporting the sharing of non-proprietary information</p>	<p>Virtual Learning and Sharing Centre making available the roadmap and all the knowledge acquired during the project</p>	<p>Number of registered users having actively accessed and used the portal by M36</p>	<p>30 organizations and 200 individuals</p>	<p>None yet, planned for later in the project</p>	
<p>Stakeholder interaction</p>	<p>Sessions of collaborative work will be held with the Local (L) and Project (P) CoPs and synergies created within the Trans- project CoPs.</p> <p>Targets and reported numbers include both physical and virtual events.</p>	<p>L-CoP: No. of events</p> <p>P- CoP: No. of events</p> <p>Trans project CoP: number of connected communities</p>	<p>Local CoP: 15</p> <p>Project CoP: 12</p> <p>Trans project CoP: 3</p>	<p>L-CoP: 6</p> <p>P-CoP: 4</p> <p>Trans-CoP: 1 (CIRSEAU)</p>	

